

Thermally driven resistive switching in solution-processable thin films of coordination polymers

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Abstract

Metal–organic coordination polymers (CPs) downsized to thin films with controllable electrical conductivity are promising for electronic device applications. Here we demonstrate, for the first time, thermally driven resistive switching in thin films of semiconducting CPs consisting of silver ion and tetracyanoquinodimethane ligand (AgTCNQ). High-quality and highly hydrophobic thin films of Ag-TCNQ were fabricated through a layer-by-layer approach upon sacrificing a pre-deposited layer of Cu-TCNQ on a thiolated Au substrate. Reversible switching between the high-resistance state (HRS) at 300 K and the low-resistance state (LRS) at 400 K with an enhancement factor of as high as $\sim 10^6$ in the electrical resistance was realized.¹ The phenomenon is attributed to the alternation of the Schottky barrier at the metal–semiconductor interface by thermal energy and not due to the formation of a conductive filament. Our discovery of thermally driven resistive switching as well as sacrificial growth of CP thin films on an organically modified substrate holds promise for the development of solution-processable non-volatile memory devices.

Keywords: Coordination polymer, Resistive switching, Schottky barrier.

References:

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